

ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN AUDITING

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Abstract

Artificial intelligence stands for intelligent technology capable of processing tasks typically associated with human intelligence. During the last few years, in the digital era, after periods of growth and stagnation, artificial intelligence (AI) started expanding rapidly and being widely applied. This paper investigates the advantages and disadvantages of implementing AI in auditing, with the emphasis on challenges and opportunities arising from this technological innovation. It explains how AI remodels an auditing process, which results in task automation and overall efficiency improvement. We have learnt that investing in AI implies quality advancement and cost reduction. Nonetheless, although audit firms expect positive impacts of implementing AI in auditing, a part of the audit staff tend to oppose AI application, particularly in relation to the reliability of AI-generated conclusions.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, audit processes, audit practice.

PREDNOSTI I NEDOSTACI VEŠTAČKE INTELIGENCIJE U REVIZIJI

Apstrakt

Za veštačku inteligenciju možemo reći da predstavlja inteligentnu tehnologiju koja ima sposobnost da obavlja zadatke koji inače zahtevaju ljudsku inteligenciju. U eri digitalnog doba, veštačka inteligencija (AI) nakon perioda uspona i stagnacija, u poslednjim godinama, kreće sa naglim razvojem i širokom primenom, kao i sve većoj dostupnosti mikroprocesora pogodnih za obimna numerička izračunavanja. Ovaj rad istražuje prednosti i nedostatke AI u procese revizije, fokusirajući se na izazove i mogućnosti koji proističu iz ove tehnološke inovacije. Objasnićemo na koji način AI preoblikuje revizorske procese, automatizujući zadatke i poboljšavajući ukupnu efikasnost. Saznali smo da investicije u AI impliciraju poboljšan kvalitet i smanjenje troškova. Iako revizorske kompanije očekuju pozitivne efekte od primene

AI na poslovima revizije, ima tendencija koje pokazuju da jedan deo zaposlenih u reviziji ima negodovanje prema primeni AI, posebno u slučajevima verodostojnosti mašinskih zaključaka. **KLjučne reči:** veštačka inteligencije, revizorski procesi, revizijska praksa

INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence (AI) is a general term used for intelligent technology. The term 'intelligent' implies that artificial intelligence is capable of thinking, learning, and performing tasks similar to those performed by humans (Kommunuri, 2022). It has helped transform multiple professions, including auditing, which has resulted in significant changes to traditional practice and processes. Implementation of artificial intelligence in audit activities guarantees increased efficiency, accuracy, and capacity for detecting anomalies, which can upgrade the quality and reliability of audit reports. Nonetheless, this integration also imposes various challenges and potential risks that must be thoroughly investigated in order to assure reliability, ethics, and regulatory alignment in auditing (Jaksic & Pestovic, 2024).

For a long time, audit firms have been showing a tendency to develop internal procedures and analytical techniques based on the application of modern technologies, for the purpose of positioning themselves better in the market and increasing their importance in business circles as technologically advanced, experienced, and professionally competent consultants that can improve operations. Implementation of artificial intelligence in auditing provides opportunities for improving efficiency, accuracy, and overall quality of the auditing process. Advantages and disadvantages related to this integration need to be addressed with caution, together with the need for adequate auditors' training and skill development. The fundamental usefulness of artificial intelligence applications in auditing lies in the concept of audit opinion relativity. The entire concept of audit opinion is based upon the concept of relative rather than absolute assurance.

APPLYING ROBOTICS IN AUDITING

There is plenty of research (Budimir, 2024; Jaksic & Pestovic, 2024; Jeremic et al., 2021) on applying artificial intelligence in the planning and implementation of auditing assignments. Robotization of auditing is not a new concept in the auditing profession. It arose from the need to accelerate auditing procedures while maintaining a sufficient level of reliability and relevance for professional assurance. Robotization of auditing could simplify data collection and analysis, which in turn could potentially simplify auditing processes and procedures, leaving more time for making conclusions (Jakovljevic, 2021a).

Since robotization would replace the structured, long-lasting, and repetitive activities performed by auditors, auditing itself should become more efficient. Additionally, auditors would have more time to carry out complex testing that includes investigation of omissions in accounting, which would also contribute to improved effectiveness of audit (Dietvorst & Bharti, 2020).

Among other things, robotization in auditing should aim at shortening the time needed to execute audit engagements and increasing the efficiency and effectiveness of audit

procedures that typically involve work-intensive, long-lasting, and repetitive testing (Guggenmos et al., 2018). Artificial intelligence is superior in terms of time saving, cost reduction, and productivity increase (Pavaloiu, 2018). Information obtained in this manner, as well as preliminary conclusions, shorten the time needed for adequate implementation of audit engagement, which results in increased net profit of the audit firm with preserved high-level objectivity and accuracy of audit conclusions. In this way, the auditors can focus on other important issues and have enough time to make a competent decision on whether financial statements contain material errors.

The digital revolution resulting from technological developments demands the evolution of business processes. The auditing profession must evolve so as to survive and be able to satisfy the needs of a transformed business environment (Ilidiz & Agdeniz, 2019). In auditing, artificial intelligence technology is widely applied in the analysis of large amounts of data due to faster data collection from one or more sources and faster conclusion-making based on the collected data, using multiple criteria and a history of similarly obtained conclusions (Jakovljevic, 2021b). Conclusions made by applying artificial intelligence technology reduce the level of subjectivity in audit judgement and increase the reliability of audit findings, considerably reducing audit errors.

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN AUDITING

Artificial intelligence gives auditors the opportunity to overcome traditional limited capacities in data processing and analysis, providing them with new dimensions due to insight into complex financial structures. Integration of artificial intelligence into the auditing process represents a revolutionary step towards improvement of efficiency, accuracy, and capacity for detecting irregularities within companies' financial and operational systems (Jaksic & Pestovic, 2024). Implementation of artificial intelligence in auditing can be realized in various phases of auditing, including audit planning, audit risk assessment, control testing, audit execution, and audit report. Regarding identification of high-risk areas, artificial intelligence enables auditors to focus their resources on potential risk zones (Ganapathy, 2023). When assessing risks, machine learning algorithms can recognize complex patterns and anomalies that are perhaps not so evident to auditors, thus making the risk assessment more accurate.

During the control testing phase, artificial intelligence tools may help with understanding the internal control system, recognizing system weaknesses, creating a process and document strategy, as well as designing control tests. In the execution phase, artificial intelligence can analyse multiple transactions in real time, identifying potential irregularities or fraud that require a more detailed analysis. In the audit report phase, artificial intelligence can support the creation of an audit report by offering a comprehensive analysis of collected data and by helping auditors make informed conclusions (Jaksic & Pestovic, 2024). Tools and technologies of artificial intelligence used in auditing include machine learning, natural language processing, expert systems, and deep learning. Machine learning gives algorithms the opportunity to learn from data and to foresee the outcomes without explicit programming, while natural language processing gives machines the capacity to understand and interpret

human language, facilitating analysis of unstructured data such as e-mails, reports, and notes. Expert systems use experts' knowledge and experience to make conclusions, while deep learning uses complex neural networks for data analysis with a high degree of precision and detail. Artificial intelligence can process and analyse large amounts of data faster than auditors, reducing the time needed for audits and giving auditors the opportunity to focus on more complex aspects of an audit. Integration of artificial intelligence into the auditing process is a key step towards modernization and improvement of auditing practice. Even though the implementation of artificial intelligence entails challenges, including the necessity for expertise and change management, the advantages that it provides concerning efficiency, accuracy, and fraud detection suggest that artificial intelligence will have a key role in shaping the future of this profession.

THE ADVANTAGES OF APPLYING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN AUDITING

The advantages of using artificial intelligence in auditing include increased efficiency, accuracy, and capacity for fraud detection. Accuracy is improved due to the capacity of artificial intelligence to identify and analyse patterns and anomalies that traditional methods would have perhaps failed to detect. The ability of artificial intelligence to continuously learn and adapt to new information also improves its capacity for fraud detection, thus providing auditing with additional reliability and assurance.

Research (Agrawal, 2023) specifies numerous advantages of applying artificial intelligence in the auditing profession:

Better audit quality – The ability of artificial intelligence to assess huge amounts of data quickly and accurately improves audit quality to a great extent, reducing the error and omission probability. Auditors use artificial intelligence for data analysis in order to identify potential problems and risks, focusing on areas that require additional testing and reducing the risk of failing to detect critical problems.

Improved efficiency – Artificial intelligence integration optimizes various manual assignments such as data input and analysis, which results in increased efficiency. This technology not only analyses data at the speed of lightning, but it also detects hidden patterns, such as constellations waiting to be discovered. Automation gives auditors the opportunity to work faster and more efficiently, which gives them more time for complex assignments that require human expertise.

Cost reduction – Automation of former manual processes by artificial intelligence contributes to savings in the auditing process. The efficiency of artificial intelligence at work shortens the audit time, which results in a reduction of the total costs. Artificial intelligence can identify specific areas that require targeted testing, optimizing resource allocation, and reducing the time and resources needed for the audit.

Advanced analytics – Artificial intelligence provides superior analytical opportunities, enabling auditors to detect complex trends and patterns that cannot be easily noticed by manual methods. By analysing comprehensive financial data sets, artificial intelligence efficiently identifies potential fraud, supporting auditors in the detection of irregularities that might not have been detected by traditional methods.

Improved risk assessment – Artificial intelligence has a key role in improving risk assessment during an audit. By analysing large amounts of financial data, artificial intelligence gives auditors the opportunity for a deeper understanding of the financial condition of the company and for potential risks. This insight enables auditors to focus their testing on high-risk areas where material errors are more likely to occur, which makes the audit targeted and more efficient.

The advantages of AI integration into the auditing practice are multiple, and they include increased efficiency and accuracy, improved capacity for fraud detection, and reduced audit time. In that way, the auditors can give full attention to more complex aspects of the audit, which gives additional value to their services. Application of artificial intelligence results in better accuracy, reliability, and timeliness of financial reporting, which is essential for financial markets' integrity and investors' trust.

Artificial intelligence offers advanced tools that enable organizations and auditors to anticipate challenges and proactively develop new solutions. By using the full potential of artificial intelligence when analysing data, auditors improve their own decision-making processes, which makes their audit engagements more proactive and of higher quality. Therefore, the advantage of AI is also its capacity to simplify audit procedures and audit processes.

THE DISADVANTAGES OF APPLYING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN AUDITING

Here we shall investigate the limitations of artificial intelligence in the context of the potential leakage of confidential information. Due to increasing complexity and modernization of business processes, the concept of trade secret is more and more often mentioned, and its legal protection is becoming imperative in our legal and business practice. The crucial issue here is how to reconcile the innovative AI potential with the trade secret confidentiality. Many AI systems require input of large amounts of data for training and functioning, which may lead to unintentional exposure of confidential information. This situation creates tension between the desire for technological progress and the need for the company's intellectual property protection.

Trade secret received its first special legal protection in the last decade of the 20th century on the international level in the form of adoption of the Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (WIPO, 2024) concluded at the same time as the Agreement Establishing the World Trade Organization on 15.04.1994 in Marrakesh. The next important international legal source was Directive 2016/943 of the European Parliament and Council from 08.05.2016 (EU, 2016) on the protection of undisclosed know-how and business information against their unlawful acquisition, use, and disclosure.

In the Serbian legal system, trade secret is regulated by several laws covering their multiple aspects, including their role in the business circles and their protection depending on the role assigned to them by those laws. They include the Law on Trade Secret Protection, the Law on Banks that also contains specifics on trade secret protection, the Labour Law, and the Criminal Code, while in practice, the Non-

Disclosure Agreement regulating trade secret protection is more and more often used together with a basic contract mutually concluded between the contracted parties.

Integration of AI into the existing framework represents a new challenge that must be carefully observed. The key problem lies in the fact that the upload of data on external AI platforms could be interpreted as unauthorized information disclosure, which directly opposes the internal policies of most companies. Once the data is uploaded to the external platform, a company loses direct control of that data, which opens up the possibility for potential misuse (Jeremic, 2024).

Such a scenario brings up plenty of legal and ethical dilemmas. On one hand, companies are obliged to protect their trade secrets, while on the other hand, limiting access to data can considerably reduce AI system efficiency. The solution to this problem requires a multidisciplinary approach:

- On a technical level,
- On the organizational level, and
- From the legal aspect.

Consequently, it must be emphasized that AI integration brings along some challenges, including the necessity for auditors to possess certain knowledge and skills, and particularities concerning data privacy and safety. Clear guidelines are required that would regulate the AI application in audit and ensure transparency, responsibility and protection of interest of all the concerned parties.

Future research in this area should concentrate on the development of methodologies that will assure safe integration of AI into a cooperative environment, but also on the analysis of long-term effects of this technology on the concept of trade secret in the digital world. Furthermore, it is necessary to investigate how the auditing profession can adjust to fast changes caused by artificial intelligence, including the need for new skills and training of auditors.

CONCLUSION

This paper shows that integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into the auditing profession results in significant changes that define work methods, processes, and the very essence of the audit. Since the auditees are using advanced technologies more and more, people engaged in audit are facing the increasing pressure in the sense of necessity for adopting new knowledge on modern technologies in order to keep their professional expertise at a satisfactory level while ensuring a sufficient level of independence and objectivity in professional assurance. Since AI uses algorithms for identifying and interpreting patterns and anomalies within data sets, it is considered to be able to assist persons engaged in auditing to identify risk areas with greater effectiveness and efficiency as well as to carry out many other tasks much faster than by using traditional techniques (Eulerich et al., 2021). An artificial intelligence system will not be perfect in its initial implementation because training takes time. At each AI activation, it gathers additional info on data that it detects and becomes better equipped to differentiate between relevant and irrelevant information. Organizations need to develop an artificial intelligence culture that represents the integration of education and constant development. Audit firms should provide vision and

guidelines for artificial intelligence projects, and employees should be aware of the concern for data confidentiality and should be open to redefining the problem under investigation (Jeremic et al., 2021).

Integration of AI into auditing represents a crucial step towards modernization and improvement of auditing practice. Although the implementation of artificial intelligence brings certain insecurities and fears, the advantages it provides concerning efficiency, accuracy, and fraud detection make this technology an inseparable part of the future. As technology will continue to develop, so shall the auditing profession have to be ready to adapt and adopt new technologies and approaches to maximize benefits and efficiently manage the challenges that artificial intelligence brings.

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REZIME

Veštačka inteligencija (AI) predstavlja naprednu tehnologiju koja poseduje sposobnost da obavlja zadatke koji su tradicionalno zahtevali ljudsku inteligenciju, kao što su prepoznavanje obrazaca, donošenje odluka, obrada jezika i učenje na osnovu podataka. U savremenom digitalnom dobu, nakon više decenija razvoja, povremenih stagnacija i uspona, veštačka inteligencija doživljava nagli tehnološki napredak, praćen širokom i ubrzanom primenom u različitim sektorima privrede i društva. Ključni faktor ovog napretka leži u znatno većoj dostupnosti računarskih resursa, naročito mikroprocesora i grafičkih jedinica pogodnih za intenzivna numerička izračunavanja, što je omogućilo primenu složenih algoritama u realnom vremenu. Ovaj rad ima za cilj da istraži prednosti i nedostatke primene veštačke inteligencije u procesu revizije, uz poseban osvrt na izazove i mogućnosti koje ova tehnološka inovacija sa sobom nosi. Analiziramo načine na koje AI transformiše revizijske procese, posebno kroz automatizaciju rutinskih i repetitivnih zadataka, čime se povećava efikasnost rada i omogućava auditorima da se fokusiraju na kompleksnije analitičke i savetodavne aktivnosti. Uočeno je da investicije u AI tehnologije donose značajna poboljšanja u pogledu kvaliteta revizije, istovremeno doprinoseći smanjenju operativnih troškova. Međutim, i pored prepoznatih koristi, određeni izazovi ostaju prisutni. Istraživanja i prikupljeni podaci ukazuju na to da, iako revizorske kompanije očekuju pozitivne efekte od implementacije AI alata u svom radu, postoji određeni stepen otpora među zaposlenima. Taj otpor se najčešće manifestuje kroz skepticizam u pogledu verodostojnosti i pouzdanosti zaključaka koje donosi mašina, naročito u kontekstu kompleksnih i subjektivnih procena koje zahtevaju ljudski uvid i profesionalni sud. Ove tendencije ukazuju na potrebu za dodatnom edukacijom, ali i za razvojem regulatornih i etičkih okvira koji će omogućiti uspešnu i odgovornu integraciju veštačke inteligencije u revizijsku praksu.